

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure
PLUS

A report detailing the pan-European continental scale terrestrial ecosystem model

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Summary

In this deliverable, we describe the setup of a terrestrial ecosystem model, the Community Land Model 5 (CLM5), over continental Europe in the framework of the eLTER RI.

For this setup, we first create input data of atmospheric conditions and static land surface information in 3 km resolution and conduct a long-term carbon cycle spin-up for adequate initial conditions of the carbon pools. Then, we evaluate our model results by comparing in-situ observations from eLTER with model data and identify caveats by analyzing the scale differences and data processing methods.

To evaluate the simulated ecosystem processes from the European CLM5, we leverage the co-location with data on energy, water, and carbon fluxes from the ICOS RI spanning the whole station network on the continent and the years 1995 to 2018. The evaluation includes the grid level and the plant functional type (PFT) level of CLM5 data. We find that the CLM5 PFT level has a lower systematic bias than the CLM5 grid level, indicating a positive effect of the functional disaggregations in CLM5.

Furthermore, we determine Europe's water-use efficiency (WUE) trends from the European CLM5 and remote sensing data and discover significantly decreasing WUE trends in Central and Eastern Europe. The observations confirmed the decreasing WUE in Central Europe, but the underrepresentation of the station network in Eastern Europe hampered the validation of our simulations.

Finally, we outline further activities where the eLTER RI and the European CLM5 can find synergies, including finding recommendations of focus regions for the RI network design, drought analysis, data assimilation, and creating an ecosystem reanalysis streamlining a data service to users of the RI. To conclude, we emphasize the substantial impact on continental, eco-hydrological research that eLTER already has as an emergent RI, and the high potential for impactful research with the established RI in future.

Introduction

Quantifying carbon and water fluxes between the land surface and the atmosphere is crucial for comprehending terrestrial ecosystem dynamics within a shifting climate (Friedlingstein et al. 2022; Green and Byrne 2004). The assessment of their magnitude and variability provides valuable insights into the resilience, performance, and fitness of ecosystems themselves (Kühn et al. 2021), water resource availability (Dong et al. 2023; Belleflamme et al. 2023), and the terrestrial carbon sinks and sources, which are essential for accounting in resource management and climate change mitigation efforts (Friedlingstein et al. 2022). While numerous studies have elucidated the impacts of various environmental variables, such as changes in temperature and precipitation, on related ecosystem processes (Bai et al. 2021; Jung et al. 2010; Massmann, Gentine, and Lin 2019), discrepancies often arise among different data sources regarding the magnitude and sometimes the sign of these responses.

Moreover, the intricate interplay of confounding factors, such as compound drought events and human influence, and controlling factors like land cover type, hydro-climate, and biodiversity, adds a layer of complexity to our understanding (Zscheischler and Seneviratne 2017; Poppe Terán et al. 2023; Díaz et al. 2022). To understand the multivariate impacts on ecosystem processes holistically, we first need harmonized continental scale in-situ observations across research disciplines. These local observations integrate biotic, abiotic, and socio-ecological spheres (Mirtl et al. 2018). Such observations should represent a vast and heterogeneous extent of the land surface. The eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI) aims to systematically deliver these insights for the European continent.

The assessment of historical and prospective changes in ecosystem processes holds particular significance in Europe, given the recently documented surge in the frequency and severity of droughts — a trend expected to amplify in the future (Lehner et al. 2017; Dai 2013; Suarez-Gutierrez, Müller, and Marotzke 2023). Notably, the densely populated network of observation sites across Europe empowers a comprehensive and large-scale analysis of the impact of droughts on ecosystems. Indeed, observational surveys have already unveiled the profound effects of recent drought years on ecosystem processes (Graf et al. 2020).

Within the eLTER RI, the diverse observed ecosystems provide a unique opportunity to discern the signals of drought response across various functional vegetation types. Furthermore, including biodiversity and socio-ecological factors in the eLTER RI's records enables studies to unravel their influence on ecosystem processes. Another substantial advantage lies in the extensive co-location with the established Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS) RI. This strategic alignment fosters a more holistic consideration of ecosystems, aligning with the Whole-Systems Approach concept (WAILS, Mirtl et al. 2021) within eLTER and ensuring access to pertinent homogenous data (Futter et al. 2023).

However, the current spatial coverage and representativeness of the site network of the emerging RI constrain the scalability of locally observed impacts (Wohner et al. 2021). Regions and ecosystem types lacking representation in the RI may experience crucial trends not captured by observational studies. Consequently, the upscaling results for larger domains, such as the entire European

continent, raise questions about their validity. In this context, it becomes imperative to integrate additional data sources for robustly understanding the detected signals in in-situ observations.

Process-based land surface models (LSMs) offer a potential solution by providing spatiotemporally consistent data, shedding light on ecosystem process variability in areas where observation RIs have limited or no representation. The consistent representation over time and space facilitates interpretability for specific user-relevant domains, such as a group of European countries.

Moreover, while research reliant solely on observational data is confined to historical periods, LSMs can project ecosystem processes into future scenarios taking into account climate and land use changes and possible management strategies. Another forecasting application is storyline simulations focussing on particular events (e.g., drought) to analyze the resilience of ecosystems to this event. Besides, LSMs can be used for short-term to seasonal forecasting, thus providing information for decision support systems and enabling actionable knowledge. Incorporating LSMs into the eLTER RI context can provide researchers with long-term, uninterrupted time-series data of ecosystem variables, particularly valuable in disciplines where observations are scarce, challenging, and expensive. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that data from LSMs carry uncertainties, including parameter complexity, model structure, and the incorporation of simplified concepts (Fisher and Koven 2020). The current understanding of the processes implemented and calibrated into the model primarily relies on in-situ observation data (D. M. Lawrence et al. 2018). Therefore, continuous evaluation of ecosystem processes in LSMs with in-situ observation data and state-of-the-art methods to enhance model accuracy, such as data assimilation, are increasingly significant.

In summary, enhanced eLTER RI services that enable the integration of in-situ data with LSM outputs hold great potential to streamline robust and impactful large-scale ecosystem research.

Motivated by these considerations, this deliverable, eLTER PLUS D9.3, related to the eLTER PLUS WP9.3, delineates establishing a pan-European ecosystem model and evaluates its output on European ecosystem processes. This initiative aligns with the broader potential within the eLTER RI context. We employ the Community Land Model version 5, widely utilized for quantifying carbon and water fluxes at site, regional, and global scales. The setup spans a pan-European domain at high resolution (3 x 3 km), and we assess simulated ecosystem processes and functions against in-situ data from eLTER and ICOS. Additionally, we present initial applications of advanced features, such as data assimilation of soil moisture and leaf area index. Finally, we deliberate on the applicability of the continental model using eLTER data, providing recommendations for future implementation and potential services related to the eLTER RI and WAIS.

Various results of this project have already been published in scientific articles (Poppe Terán et al. 2023; Strebel et al. 2024) and the main contents of this report also refer to these previously published works.

A pan-European terrestrial ecosystem model

The Community Land Model (CLM) stands out as one of the most actively used Land Surface Models (LSMs), has a large active community, and is under ongoing development, with our application utilizing the latest version, CLM5 (D. M. Lawrence et al. 2019; 2018). Recent advancements have introduced a biogeochemistry module that resolves carbon and nitrogen fluxes and pools in vegetation and soil. This module enables the prognostic calculation of carbon and nitrogen states, an enhancement from prior methodologies that relied solely on prescribing remotely sensed Leaf Area Index (LAI) time series in last-generation LSMs. CLM5 has already played a pivotal role in investigating diverse effects on ecosystem processes, providing insights into water resource states and carbon budgets. For instance, it was used to investigate the variability of soil moisture, evapotranspiration, gross primary production, and their interactions across various scales, from single-point and regional to continental and global contexts (D. M. Lawrence et al. 2019; Boas et al. 2023; Strebel et al. 2023; Dombrowski et al. 2022).

Moreover, CLM5 can be coupled with models from other sections of the Earth system, such as ocean, atmosphere, and subsurface hydrology models. Including the biogeochemistry module is another crucial enhancement for understanding ecosystem processes, as it calculates rather than prescribes vegetation states. This shift enables a more informed exploration of vegetation response to environmental changes and facilitates better comparisons with in-situ observational data.

Operating on an ecosystem scale at single-point, regional, and global domains, CLM5 outputs variables at multiple levels, including on grid cells, soil columns, and plant functional types (PFTs). This adaptability aligns well with the Whole System Approach for in-situ research on Life Supporting Systems (WAILS) research approach within eLTER, facilitating upscaling local or network-wide information to spatially and temporally consistent robust data.

Furthermore, a European CLM5 interfaces with all eLTER research spheres:

- **Sociosphere**, including human management in cropland units (harvest, fertilization) and forest PFTs (harvest).
- **Biosphere**, by aggregating information around plant species abundance into groups of functional types.
- **Hydrosphere**, it outputs hydrological variables and can potentially couple with more sophisticated surface and subsurface hydrological models.
- **Geosphere**, it resolves carbon and nitrogen fluxes in soil and vegetation prognostically within the biogeochemistry module.
- **Atmosphere**, by including atmospheric forcing data and their trends and their impacts on the land surface.

Looking ahead, the eLTER RI aims to support land surface model research in Europe across different scales. The evaluation of eLTER within the framework of a European CLM5 setup serves to identify strengths, weaknesses, and potential bottlenecks critical for transitioning to operational status. Beyond research output, a European CLM5 setup could offer additional services to researchers, providing spatially and temporally consistent, gapless, and robust data. This resource becomes

particularly valuable for complementing observations or filling gaps in scenarios where data are unavailable.

Structure of the Community Land Model Version 5

In CLM5, a study domain encompasses one or multiple grid cells, with the number of grid cells contingent on the domain's extent and chosen spatial resolution. Each grid cell covers a specific area and utilizes static information from that location as calculation parameters. Within every grid cell, the area is further subdivided based on land cover types such as natural and managed vegetation, urban areas, lakes, and glaciers. These coverage types consist of functional types, such as plant functional types (PFT) for natural vegetation, which determine the equations and parameters employed by CLM5 during simulations (refer to [Figure 1](#)).

[Figure 2](#) illustrates the critical simulated processes in CLM5, encompassing the land surface energy balance, surface and subsurface hydrology, and biogeochemical processes like transpiration and photosynthesis. For a prognostic evaluation of ecosystem processes—specifically, the energy, water, carbon, and nitrogen cycles — CLM5 recently incorporated the biogeochemical cycles module (CLM5-BGC). Previously, limited information was available, mainly inferred from remotely sensed vegetation states such as LAI. However, in CLM5-BGC, these states are now calculated from the bottom: photosynthesis assimilates atmospheric carbon into vegetation based on environmental conditions and then allocates it to plant organs. The carbon allocated to the leaves determines the LAI. Simultaneously, nitrogen serves a dual role as fertilizer and a potential growth-limiting factor for vegetation when unavailable. For more details and the empirical and numerical implementations of the processes, we refer to (D. M. Lawrence et al. 2018).

Figure 1: Disaggregation of space and function in CLM5. Grid cells are subdivided into land units, again into soil columns, and finally into plant or crop functional types (PFT or CFT, respectively). For more information, please refer to (D. M. Lawrence et al. 2019; 2018)

Figure 2: Simulated processes in CLM5 on the ecosystem, plant, and landscape level (D. M. Lawrence et al. 2019; 2018).

European study domain

In our CLM5 simulation, we define the simulation domain to encompass the European CORDEX region ((EURO-CORDEX 2009), refer to [Figure 3](#)). This domain grid is curvilinear, designed to comprise equal-area grid cells. This design is advantageous for atmospheric modeling and facilitates spatial analysis through unit area considerations (as well as up and downscaling) in land surface modeling. Moreover, the chosen extent aligns with outputs from downscaling and reanalysis projects of climate data, allowing for the straightforward utilization of high-resolution atmospheric forcings.

Building on prior work within this domain, specifically using CLM3.5 (Naz et al. 2020), we set up the grid at a resolution of 3 kilometers. As a result, the domain encompasses 1,592 grid cells in the x-direction (approximately corresponding to longitude) and 1,544 grid cells in the y-direction (roughly corresponding to latitude). It is important to note that, of these grid cells, only those containing land surfaces will undergo simulation in CLM5, while ocean grid cells are masked. This approach ensures a focused and relevant simulation within the specified geographical bounds.

Figure 3: Extent of the European CORDEX domain (blue shaded area). The curved borders are due to the curvilinear grid, which ensures an equal area for all grid cells.

The simulated area of the model spans a diverse geographical range, extending from Morocco in the southwest, the Red Sea in the southeast, Iceland in the northwest, and Siberia in the northeast. This expansive region captures a broad hydro-climatic gradient, encompassing notable features such as the arid Mediterranean to the very humid Alps and Nordic mountains. The gradient ranges from very arid areas in Southern Europe to very humid regions in the Alps and Northern Europe (refer to [Figure 4](#)).

The geographical diversity of ecological conditions, defined by hydro-climates and various other environmental factors, can be mirrored by the distribution of Plant Functional Types (PFTs) across the continent (refer to [Figure 5](#)). For instance, vast areas of Boreal Needleleaf Evergreen Forests are found in the North, while Central and Eastern Europe host patches of Mixed Forests and Temperate Evergreen and Deciduous Forests. However, a significant portion of the land surface is dominated by unmanaged, unirrigated croplands, i.e. agricultural fields that are rainfed and not fertilized. Notably, substantial areas lack vegetation coverage, constituting bare ground, particularly evident in the very arid regions of Northern Africa to Israel and the barren land surrounding Icelandic volcanoes.

We masked the grid cells dominated by bare ground and areas with a very arid hydro-climate for most analyses. Masking very arid regions or bare land areas aims to concentrate our studies on vegetation functions, such as the water-use efficiency (as shown in [Figure 4](#) and [Figure 5](#)). It is essential to acknowledge that this domain extends beyond the geographical and political borders of the European continent. This extension should be considered when scaling data and results to the European user context in eLTER.

Figure 4: Hydro-climate based on annual precipitation from the COSMO reanalysis 6 across the European CORDEX domain. The categories are slightly modified from (Jafari et al. 2018). Figure 11 shows the locations and hydro-climates of eLTER stations that offered relevant data for this work.

Figure 5. The dominant plant functional type (PFT) by area for each grid cell in the pan-European model domain. Aside from the displayed PFT, other PFTs might be present that have a lower area coverage, which might, however, still contribute significantly to the grid scale processes. NET: Needleleaf Evergreen Tree, NDF: Needleleaf Deciduous Tree, BET: Broadleaf Evergreen Tree, BDT: Broadleaf Deciduous Tree, BES: Broadleaf Evergreen Shrub, BDS: Broadleaf Deciduous Shrub, UCrop: Unmanaged Crop, Ulrr: Unirrigated, Irr: Irrigated.

Carbon model spin-up

To simulate carbon pools of vegetation and soil (e.g., leaf carbon, soil organic matter) and fluxes (e.g., gross primary production) for the analysis period (1995 - 2018), first establishing initial conditions for each carbon pool, Plant Functional Type (PFT), and soil column in every land surface grid cell is essential. Traditionally, a spin-up simulation achieves this — a long-term process that commences from arbitrary states and evolves all carbon pools until a steady state is reached. Carbon equilibrium signifies a state where an ecosystem releases the same amount of carbon it absorbs, depending upon the prevailing climatic and environmental conditions.

While the carbon cycle constantly adapts during changing environmental conditions and is rarely in true equilibrium, assuming an equilibrium state during spin-up is necessary to eliminate trends resulting from the default arbitrary initial conditions. This factor becomes particularly crucial in regions experiencing dynamic shifts (e.g., due to human management) or gradual trends (e.g., temperature and atmospheric CO₂).

Constrained by the availability of atmospheric forcing data, our spin-up simulations are designed to cycle the forcing data for 1995 - 2012 (18 years) until equilibrium is reached. We define equilibrium thresholds on the continental level:

- 1. Negligible change of the total ecosystem carbon across the domain:**

$$\Delta C_{tot, Europe} < 2 \text{ Tg C year}^{-1}$$

Where $\Delta C_{tot, Europe}$ is the difference between the total carbon pool size over Europe averaged over the last cycling period of 18 years and the same value for the previous cycling period.

- 2. 97% of the individual grid cells must be in equilibrium.** For each grid cell, we checked if

$$\Delta C_{tot, cell} < 1 \text{ g C m}^2 \text{ year}^{-1}$$

Where $\Delta C_{tot, cell}$ is the difference between the carbon pool size of an individual grid cell over the last cycling period of 18 years and the same value for the previous cycling period.

The total soil organic matter pool (vertically across soil layers) and the total vegetation carbon (aggregated across plant tissues, including roots, stems, and leaves, and across plant functional types) were critical to these evaluations.

In our setup, the second threshold was particularly pivotal. Specific grid cells in the northern regions of Europe exhibited a slow evolution towards equilibrium points, likely attributable to prolonged turnover times in colder temperatures. Eventually, after approximately 1500 simulation years, both requirements for continental-level equilibrium were met. The resulting carbon states are the equilibrium conditions and were then employed as initial conditions for subsequent production simulations.

It is worth noting that ongoing efforts are being made to refine the spin-up design and explore alternative methods to determine suitable equilibrium states. These endeavors are part of

continuous improvements in our European CLM5 approach. We discuss these in more detail in the Outlook chapter.

Input data

Crucially, the input data for the model originates from external sources and carries varying degrees of uncertainty. For example, CLM5 relies on static maps derived from remote sensing data to determine the abundance of each Plant Functional Type (PFT) across our model domain. The satellite images may have a relatively coarse resolution, and the methodology for partitioning an optical signal into information for different PFTs might rely on uncertain assumptions. Consequently, it is essential to thoroughly assess the utilized input data and consistently explore potentially more suitable and accurate alternatives.

In this context, we describe the data used in the initial setup of the European CLM5-BGC model. Rigorous scrutiny and refinements are part of our approach, ensuring the model remains responsive to advancements in data quality and methodologies. Recommendations for enhancements in input data for future implementations are outlined in the Outlook section. Generally, input data for land surface models can be broadly categorized into surface information and atmospheric forcing data.

Surface information

Ecosystem processes resolved in CLM5-BGC depend on information and parameters derived from soil and vegetation characteristics. While these properties may change over various time scales, this European CLM5 assumes they are static. For instance, soil hydrological processes are parameterized based on soil texture and soil structure variables, and equations and parameters for calculating water and carbon fluxes in the biosphere depend upon present vegetation and crop types.

In the initial setup of the European CLM5-BGC, we utilize the default surface information embedded in the CLM5 standard repository. [Table 1](#) outlines the most crucial surface input variables, and for a more comprehensive understanding, additional details can be referenced in the technical note of CLM5 (D. M. Lawrence et al. 2018). Notably, the direct calculation of vegetation states through carbon pools and fluxes in the BGC module allows for a more functional consideration of the vegetation responses to a dynamic environment.

Table 1: Static surface input data used for the European CLM5-BGC model. All surface input data are from standard CLM5 repositories. More information on all fields can be found in the CLM5 technical manual by D. M. Lawrence et al. 2018.

	Resolution	Reference
Soil texture	0,08°	IGBP, 2000
PFT distribution	0.05°	P. J. Lawrence and Chase, 2007
Slope and elevation	1 km	Earth Resources Observation And Science (EROS) Center, 2017

Atmospheric forcing

When employing a land surface model, the meteorological variables influencing the land surface are prescribed. Typically, these variables include solar incoming longwave and shortwave radiation, near-surface air temperature, pressure, wind speed, humidity, and precipitation. While in-situ observations can be utilized for single-point simulations, upscaling them for large-scale domains is challenging. Instead, spatially uniform meteorological forcings can be derived from global climate model outputs, remote sensing-based data, or reanalysis methods.

In our case, we leverage the high-resolution output of the COSMO Reanalysis 6, which provides data over the European CORDEX domain at a resolution of 6 kilometers from 1995 to 2018. This reanalysis combines the COSMO model with multivariate data assimilation using a nudging method (Bollmeyer et al. 2015). The boundary conditions for this reanalysis are derived from the discontinued ERA-Interim global reanalysis, which has a coarser resolution of 79 kilometers. A key advantage of COSMO Reanalysis 6 is its improved representation of seasonal precipitation intensities and extreme events compared to other, coarser data (Bollmeyer et al. 2015; Wahl et al. 2017). This feature is particularly beneficial for accurately capturing surface and subsurface hydrological fluxes, especially in regions with relatively heterogeneous vegetation and soil patches.

It is worth noting that a newer version of the COSMO Reanalysis 6, using the more recent ERA5 reanalysis and covering additional recent years, is currently under development at DWD (German Weather Service). This newer version can be considered for future European CLM5 setups and reflects the commitment to improving data inputs and enhancing the accuracy of simulations.

Uniting the Model and RI data

Evaluation Data

Before delving into more intricate analyses using the CLM5 outputs, it is essential to contextualize them through a comparison with time series of ground truth data derived from in-situ observations. In this initial assessment, we scrutinize how the simulations capture the observed mean magnitude, variability, seasonal transitions, peaks, troughs, and extreme values of ecosystem variables. We leverage Eddy Covariance (EC) station observations to achieve this.

The EC technique measures the vertical exchange of energy, water, and carbon between ecosystem-scale patches of the land surface beneath a measurement tower. Tower height, wind speed, and wind direction influence the footprint of these measurements on the land surface. Ensuring a relatively homogeneous land surface — characterized by vegetation corresponding to a single land cover type — within one km² circle around the tower ensures a consistent account of functional responses to environmental conditions in the observation data.

A consolidated call in eLTER PLUS invited multiple EC stations participating in eLTER to contribute data for eLTER PLUS Task 9.3. While several sites submitted relevant data, most station Principal Investigators (PIs) noted that their EC data is publicly available through the ICOS RI's Data Portal. This strategic alignment with ICOS reflects eLTER's commitment to leveraging physical and digital co-location with other RIs, such as ICOS, to facilitate holistic research within the framework of WAILS.

ICOS offers EC data adhering to a meticulous instrument, measurement, and processing protocol, ensuring information consistency and quantified uncertainty. Importantly, the provided data is homogenized, sharing a consistent format across all sites. This harmonization across the sites eliminates the need for researchers to undertake data harmonization steps before analysis, streamlining implementation into their workflows. Furthermore, ICOS encompasses several countries and EC sites not currently participating in eLTER, enhancing the representativity for the European CLM5 evaluation. For this purpose, we utilize the comprehensive and curated ICOS data "Warm Winter 2020," consisting of 73 sites and over 800 station-years (Warm Winter 2020 Team and ICOS Ecosystem Thematic Centre 2022).

Thus, EC data facilitates a direct comparison between data from EC stations and the CLM5 at the scale of PFT or grid cells (CLM_{PFT} and CLM_{grid}, respectively), eliminating the need for any downscaling or upscaling data sources. Such a methodology enhances the reliability of the evaluation, providing a robust basis for further analyses and insights into the model's performance.

The following outlines the steps taken to ensure comparability between ICOS EC station Gross Primary Production (GPP) and evapotranspiration (ET), which are the main processes cycling water, energy, and carbon through the ecosystem, and corresponding data from our European CLM5 outputs:

1. **Land Cover Exclusion:** Although wetland is a functional land unit in CLM5, it did not appear in the CLM5 setup over Europe. Consequently, stations over wetlands and stations where we did not find official land cover information were omitted from the analyses. We also exclude

shrubland sites to focus on Europe's most predominant land cover: Forests, grasslands, and croplands.

2. **Mixed Forest Handling:** Given that there is no PFT specifically designated for mixed forest land cover in CLM5, those stations were also excluded. CLM5 does not locally combine these PFTs if both Needleleaf and Broadleaf forests are present within the grid cell.
3. **Data Extraction:** We extracted daily time series for the remaining 42 stations for Gross Primary Production (GPP) and latent heat, gap-filled with the Marginal Distribution Sampling method.
4. **Handling Negative GPP Values:** Negative GPP values, while not possible by definition, are present in ICOS data as artifacts of the net ecosystem exchange (NEE) partitioning model (Reichstein et al. 2012). We retained these negative values within the uncertainty range of NEE to avoid bias in the overall GPP distribution of ICOS observations.
5. **Time Resolution Matching:** We averaged time series to 8 daily to ensure consistency across data sources.
6. **Quality Control:** A masking of the time series with corresponding quality flags in the ICOS data excludes bad-quality data from the analysis.
7. **Conversion of Latent Heat to Evapotranspiration (ET):** Latent heat values in W m^{-2} were converted to ET in mm day^{-1} using a multiplication factor of 0.035, assuming a constant enthalpy of vaporization decoupled from temperature.

These rigorous steps aim to establish a reliable basis for comparing and evaluating CLM5 outputs against high-quality ICOS EC station data, contributing to the robustness and credibility of the assessment. [Table 2](#) lists all the stations used in this work, their locations, and the coordinates of the closest cell in the grid.

Table 2: Information on the location of each station, including the coordinates of the closest grid cell in the 3 km European CORDEX grid used in our model. ENF: Evergreen Needleleaf Forest, DBF: Deciduous broadleaf forest, GRA: Grasslands, CRO: Croplands.

ID	Country	land cover	latitude (station)	longitude (station)	latitude (cell)	longitude (cell)
BE-Bra	Belgium	ENF	51.31	4.52	51.29	4.51
BE-Dor	Belgium	GRA	50.31	4.97	50.31	4.96
BE-Lcr	Belgium	DBF	51.11	3.85	51.1	3.85
BE-Lon	Belgium	CRO	50.55	4.75	50.57	4.76
CH-Cha	Switzerland	GRA	47.21	8.41	47.21	8.43
CH-Dav	Switzerland	ENF	46.82	9.86	46.8	9.84
CH-Fru	Switzerland	GRA	47.12	8.54	47.11	8.53
CH-Oe2	Switzerland	CRO	47.29	7.73	47.28	7.72
CZ-BK1	Czech Republic	ENF	49.5	18.54	49.5	18.54
CZ-Lnz	Czech Republic	DBF	48.68	16.95	48.67	16.95

DE-Geb	Germany	CRO	51.1	10.91	51.1	10.93
DE-Gri	Germany	GRA	50.95	13.51	50.95	13.49
DE-Hai	Germany	DBF	51.08	10.45	51.07	10.45
DE-HoH	Germany	DBF	52.09	11.22	52.09	11.23
DE-Kli	Germany	CRO	50.89	13.52	50.9	13.54
DE-RuR	Germany	GRA	50.62	6.3	50.62	6.28
DE-RuS	Germany	CRO	50.87	6.45	50.86	6.44
DE-RuW	Germany	ENF	50.5	6.33	50.51	6.31
DE-Tha	Germany	ENF	50.96	13.57	50.96	13.58
DK-Gds	Denmark	ENF	56.07	9.33	56.07	9.34
DK-Sor	Denmark	DBF	55.49	11.64	55.48	11.65
FI-Hyy	Finland	ENF	61.85	24.29	61.86	24.29
FI-Ken	Finland	ENF	67.99	24.24	67.99	24.23
FI-Let	Finland	ENF	60.64	23.96	60.63	23.96
FI-Var	Finland	ENF	67.75	29.61	67.76	29.63
FR-Aur	France	CRO	43.55	1.11	43.54	1.12
FR-Bil	France	ENF	44.49	-0.96	44.5	-0.98
FR-FBn	France	ENF	43.24	5.68	43.25	5.69
FR-Fon	France	DBF	48.48	2.78	48.47	2.8
FR-Gri	France	CRO	48.84	1.95	48.86	1.95
FR-Hes	France	DBF	48.67	7.06	48.67	7.05
FR-Lam	France	CRO	43.5	1.24	43.51	1.25
FR-Tou	France	GRA	43.57	1.37	43.58	1.38
IT-BFt	Italy	DBF	45.2	10.74	45.21	10.75
IT-MBo	Italy	GRA	46.01	11.05	46	11.04
IT-Ren	Italy	ENF	46.59	11.43	46.58	11.44
IT-SR2	Italy	ENF	43.73	10.29	43.74	10.31
IT-Tor	Italy	GRA	45.84	7.58	45.85	7.57
RU-Fy2	Russia	ENF	56.45	32.9	56.46	32.89

SE-Htm	Sweden	ENF	56.1	13.42	56.1	13.42
SE-Nor	Sweden	ENF	60.09	17.48	60.09	17.5
SE-Svb	Sweden	ENF	64.26	19.77	64.26	19.77

Integrating local observations in the continental scale

Spatial data, whether derived from aggregated remote sensing images or land surface model outputs, is characterized by a uniform distribution in the form of gridded data. In contrast, in-situ measurements are typically collected at a single point and represent a specific footprint area on the land surface associated with a single land cover type. It is important to note that the coordinates of a station location may not align precisely with the coordinates of any grid cell center. Therefore, when comparing spatial data and in-situ observations, careful consideration is required to determine the subset of the gridded data so that it most closely corresponds to the local observations.

While selecting the closest grid cell is the most logical approach, complexities arise depending on the land surface's heterogeneity and the gridded data's resolution. For instance, for stations near the coast, the nearest grid cell center might be masked as an ocean cell, or the land cover represented in the model may not match that of the EC station footprint (as illustrated in [Figure 6](#)). In such instances, these grid cells cannot provide corresponding data. Therefore, alternative nearby grid cells or different approaches must be considered.

Moreover, considering the latest generation LSMs, including this European CLM5, there is support for a sub-grid functional discretization of soil columns and vegetation functions. This advanced feature allows access to disaggregated data within the grid cell, facilitating a comparison of matching model PFT and the observed land cover of the EC station footprint. This procedure ensures a proper representation of observed vegetation functionality in the comparisons, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of the analyses.

The ICOS RI labels sites corresponding to the IGBP land cover categories. Incidentally, they correspond to the PFTs in CLM5. For comparison with the PFT level in CLM5, we map the selected land cover to the corresponding CLM5 PFT in [Table 3](#). When comparing site data with CLM_{PFT}, we only use the time series corresponding to the PFT related to that site's land cover.

Table 3: Mapping of IGBP land cover labels of ICOS sites to CLM5 PFT.

IGBP Landcover	Corresponding CLM5 PFT in Europe
Evergreen needleleaf forest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Needleleaf evergreen tree - boreal ● Needleleaf evergreen tree - temperate
Deciduous broadleaf forest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Broadleaf deciduous tree - boreal ● Broadleaf deciduous tree - temperate
Grasslands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● C₃ Arctic grass ● C₃ Grass ● C₄ Grass
Croplands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● C₃ unmanaged crop - rainfed ● C₃ unmanaged crop - irrigated

Figure 6: The land cover, and therefore the ecosystem functions of the in-situ station and the closest grid cell in the model might not match. The station (red dot) and the footprint in this scenario observe the ecosystem processes of a Forest. However, data from the closest grid cell (center right) represents mostly croplands. In this case, it might be adequate to compare the station data with other surrounding grid cells or access the PFT-specific time series in the sub-grid of that closest grid cell.

First applications

Having gathered surface information, atmospheric forcing data, and the initial conditions derived from the spin-up process, we conducted an initial production simulation spanning 1995 to 2018, utilizing default settings. The primary objectives of this initial simulation were as follows:

1. **Evaluation with In-Situ Data:** The outputs generated intended to serve as a basis for evaluating GPP and ET by comparing them with in-situ data from ICOS and eLTER RIs.
2. **Investigation of Variability:** We sought to investigate the simulated variability of GPP and ET across Europe, aiming to discern patterns, trends, and potential anomalies.
3. **Identification of Model Shortcomings:** The simulation aimed to identify any shortcomings in the current model setup. The outputs helped pinpoint potential improvements in inputs, parameters, and settings that could enhance accuracy and reliability.
4. **Establishment of Baseline or Control Simulation:** The results of this simulation provide a baseline or control scenario, crucial for conducting future experiments with varying settings. This baseline serves as a reference point to compare the outcomes of subsequent simulations with altered parameters or configurations.

General evaluation

In our analysis, we compare the observed time-series data from ICOS observations at various sites with corresponding time-series data from CLM_{grid} (the area-weighted average of the PFT-specific data in the closest grid cell) and CLM_{PFT} (PFT within the closest grid cell that corresponds with the station land cover). The model data covers a continuous time series from 1995 to 2018. On the other hand, the observation periods vary from site to site, with potential gaps due to missing measurements and low-quality gap filling (as outlined in the Evaluation Data section).

We adopt a meticulous approach to ensure a meaningful and consistent comparison across the same periods. We mask the model data to align with the dates where observed values are available, respecting data quality characteristics at each site. This method ensures that the comparison is based on concurrent data across the sources, allowing for a robust assessment of the model's performance against observed data.

We compute two model benchmark metrics, the first of which is the root mean square error (RMSE). This metric serves as a quantitative measure of the model's approximation to the ground truth, providing insights into the accuracy and precision of the simulated data compared to the observed values. RMSE is determined as follows:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_{sim,i} - X_{obs,i})^2}{n}}$$

Where n is the number of values in the time series, $X_{sim,i}$ is the simulated value of the variable X at the time i , and $X_{obs,i}$ is the respective observation. The unit of RMSE is the unit of X . A relatively high

RMSE value indicates that the simulations differ substantially from the observations, while a value close to 0 indicates a good approximation.

The second metric is the percent bias (PBIAS), which gives insight into whether the model generally over or underestimates the ground truth and to what degree:

$$PBIAS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_{sim,i} - X_{obs,i}}{\sum_{i=1}^n X_{obs,i}} \times 100$$

Where the variables correspond with their definition from above, negative PBIAS values mean the model generally underestimates the variable relative to the observations. In contrast, a positive value shows a general overestimation. Consequently, a PBIAS close to 0 demonstrates that the model, on average, approximates the magnitude of the observed variable well.

We calculate these metrics for each variable and station for CLM_{grid} and CLM_{PFT} . The consideration of both scales allows us to additionally evaluate the added value of the functional disaggregation of the vegetation and whether this translates to a better comparison against observations.

We incorporate additional existing and publicly available datasets to contextualize CLM5 and enhance our comparative analysis. Specifically, we include remote sensing data from the Global Land Surface Satellite (GLASS, Liang et al. 2021). Moreover, exclusively for ET, we integrate reanalysis data from the ECMWF 5 Reanalysis Land (ERA5L, Copernicus Climate Change Service 2019) and the Global Land Evaporation Amsterdam Model (GLEAM, Martens et al. 2017). These latter data sources do not offer carbon or vegetation information such as LAI or GPP, which underlines the requirement for new, comprehensive, publicly available data on vegetation states.

Table 4: Model evaluation benchmark metrics RMSE and PBIAS for GPP for each station. The conditional color formatting for RMSE is scaled between the lowest value in white and the largest value in the darkest red. The color formatting for PBIAS shows negative values in purple and positive values in green.

ID	GPP RMSE			GPP PBIAS		
	$CLM5_{grid}$	$CLM5_{PFT}$	GLASS	$CLM5_{grid}$	$CLM5_{PFT}$	GLASS
BE-Bra	2.29	1.69	1.3	-35.31	0.58	4.7
BE-Dor	3.19	3.39	2.74	-41.65	-40.27	-35.08
BE-Lon	4.31	4.31	3.98	-18.12	-8.2	-11.27
CH-Cha	4.61	3.94	4.29	-50.85	-38.48	-47.12
CH-Dav	2.4	2.13	2.13	-16.6	30.76	-25.06
CH-Fru	3.6	2.84	2.62	-39.95	-23.07	-23.89
CH-Oe2	3.75	3.95	3.53	-10.63	-12.43	2.68

CZ-BK1	2.79	2.31	1.95	-37.01	-22.8	-20.62
CZ-Lnz	4.64	3.44	2.9	-61.65	-48.99	-28.72
DE-Geb	3.63	4.32	2.98	-35.47	-39.88	-1.82
DE-Gri	2.61	2.68	2.02	-21.13	-11.9	-9.62
DE-Hai	2.83	2.59	1.7	-34.4	-41.98	-1.49
DE-HoH	2.94	2.51	3.04	-30.18	-40.09	-27.51
DE-Kli	3.5	3.66	3.15	1.73	2.03	-2.71
DE-RuR	2.4	2.39	2	-26.97	-10.45	-19.49
DE-RuS	4.74	5.05	4.34	-43.33	-45.5	-34.54
DE-RuW	2.63	2.61	2.14	-32.06	-27.58	-23.83
DE-Tha	1.87	1.48	1.29	-28.94	-3.95	-19.24
DK-Sor	4.39	4.07	3.21	-47.92	-49.59	-35.2
FI-Hyy	1.3	1.29	0.81	-14.86	-0.32	-8.87
FI-Ken	1.16	2.34	0.72	-2.71	53.03	-13.93
FI-Let	2.05	2.02	1.53	-19.04	-4.69	-19.86
FI-Var	1.4	3.22	0.89	58.88	155.55	20.97
FR-Aur	3.28	4.05	3.25	9.34	68.22	8.98
FR-Bil	1.75	2.23	1.67	-24.81	-24.43	-0.67
FR-FBn	2.38	3.73	1.82	-48.88	-77.01	15.32
FR-Fon	3.1	2.87	2.74	-26.88	-36.12	-21.86
FR-Gri	4.16	4.24	3.73	-18.64	-13.82	-15.47
FR-Hes	3.7	3.24	3.32	-24.24	-35.9	-17.18
FR-Lam	3.91	4.5	3.95	-4.08	44.74	-8.86
FR-Tou	3.44	2.53	1.77	-73.37	-47.07	-10.42
IT-MBo	2.42	2.89	1.84	-7.88	-31.82	3.25
IT-Ren	1.53	2.32	1.77	11.56	33.15	-2.03
IT-SR2	5.12	6.78	4.07	-67.17	-88.85	-53.94
IT-Tor	1.82	2.49	1.66	-0.73	1.01	1.16
RU-Fy2	2.63	2.84	1.93	-26.01	-22.21	-23.36
SE-Htm	2.74	2.24	1.95	-38.02	-25.41	-26.83

SE-Nor	1.59	1.37	1.35	-25.47	-3.78	-21.52
SE-Svb	1.13	2.02	1.22	5.6	24.88	-24.05
∅	2.92	3.04	2.39	-24.30	-11.86	-14.85

Table 5: Model evaluation benchmark metrics RMSE and PBIAS for ET for each station. The conditional color formatting for RMSE is scaled between the lowest value in white and the largest value in the darkest red. The color formatting for PBIAS shows negative values in purple and positive values in green.

ID	ET RMSE					ET PBIAS				
	<i>CLM5_{grid}</i>	<i>CLM5_{PFT}</i>	<i>ERA5L</i>	<i>GLASS</i>	<i>GLEAM</i>	<i>CLM5_{grid}</i>	<i>CLM5_{PFT}</i>	<i>ERA5L</i>	<i>GLASS</i>	<i>GLEAM</i>
BE-Bra	0.53	0.52	1.1	1.12	0.65	21.18	23.28	102.74	86.9	53.51
BE-Lon	0.65	0.99	0.92	0.83	0.48	13.44	24.31	67.7	44.85	20.31
CH-Cha	0.78	0.85	0.53	0.59	0.55	-32.31	-21.19	-13.4	-9.81	-8.37
CH-Dav	1.19	0.94	1.35	0.91	0.84	-50.35	-32.89	-54.06	-31.86	-27.21
CH-Fru	0.6	0.85	0.61	0.49	0.59	-23.14	-8.38	-6.73	-4.59	6.33
CZ-BK1	0.47	0.54	0.57	0.76	0.52	-23.38	-25.8	28.72	20.22	24.72
DE-Geb	0.51	0.83	0.86	0.71	0.48	-6.91	-5.24	64.07	40.18	14.67
DE-Gri	0.48	0.77	0.53	0.56	0.36	1.4	10.84	32.03	19.42	8.18
DE-Hai	0.48	0.6	0.75	0.72	0.5	1.23	7.5	54.25	42.96	27.83
DE-HoH	0.69	0.65	0.58	0.6	0.65	-27.75	-16.19	-1.24	-10.98	-24.17
DE-Kli	0.64	0.99	0.7	0.74	0.58	3.53	16.23	36.42	24.16	20.33
DE-RuR	0.4	0.77	0.53	0.6	0.45	-18.28	5.14	27.41	9.26	16.76
DE-RuS	0.79	0.98	0.49	0.64	0.69	-35.1	-32.57	4.96	-15.5	-27.25
DE-Tha	0.61	0.49	0.69	0.71	0.47	0.03	-0.58	39.24	20.32	13.76
DK-Sor	0.6	0.59	0.65	0.55	0.5	-25.3	-14.11	40.06	19.22	2.01
FI-Hyy	0.5	0.52	0.41	0.49	0.63	-35.03	-26.83	20.28	11.59	41.51
FI-Let	0.67	0.62	0.78	0.61	0.71	-32.63	-21.82	48.73	9.52	38.69
FI-Var	0.37	0.48	0.46	0.69	0.59	-34.03	-14.31	65.47	55.65	85.29
FR-Aur	0.81	1.18	1.03	1.08	0.75	6.82	47.61	54.17	39.04	18.56
FR-Bil	0.67	0.9	0.7	1.5	0.68	-25.39	-27.73	23.93	50.29	24.77
FR-Gri	0.76	1	0.77	0.85	0.55	-7.41	-2.62	38.22	22.79	-1.57

FR-Hes	0.58	0.67	0.86	0.83	0.72	0.92	13.76	52.3	36.7	36.96
FR-Lam	0.85	1.09	0.98	0.96	0.78	-8.52	19.85	29.34	15.93	-3.31
FR-Tou	0.7	0.9	1.05	0.87	0.5	-35.79	-45.8	61.12	31.2	17.87
IT-MBo	0.53	0.8	0.46	0.48	0.7	-2.52	-17.37	8.64	6.11	15.84
IT-Ren	0.86	0.82	0.71	0.76	0.75	-25.41	-5.21	-11.11	-17.11	-0.6
IT-SR2	0.91	1.56	0.76	0.71	0.81	-33.93	-60.78	28.67	4.92	-23.63
IT-Tor	1.03	1.14	0.87	0.65	0.84	-43.24	-46.1	-35.9	-11.77	-29.23
RU-Fy2	0.41	0.51	0.69	0.65	0.67	-3.69	-16.07	52.22	25.24	52.85
SE-Htm	0.45	0.45	0.89	1.18	0.9	-7.53	-3.65	72.62	60.16	77.51
SE-Nor	0.36	0.37	0.57	0.66	0.58	-15.2	-5.08	46.5	21.54	45.74
SE-Svb	0.46	0.6	0.33	0.52	0.56	-22.3	-4.25	14.62	14.77	33.97
∅	0.64	0.78	0.72	0.75	0.63	-16.46	-8.94	31.00	19.73	17.27

For metrics of GPP please refer to [Table 4](#) and of ET to [Table 5](#).

For GPP, the analysis reveals that CLM5 at the grid level (CLM_{grid}) often exhibits good approximations to the observations, showing a relatively low RMSE of 2.92 g C m^{-2} . This value is marginally lower than the mean RMSE of CLM at the PFT level (CLM_{pFT}), which stands at 3.04 g C m^{-2} . Nonetheless, the GLASS GPP compares better to ICOS data than both CLM5 levels.

Generally, all data sources underestimate the in-situ GPP observations (negative PBIAS). CLM_{pFT} has the lowest systematic bias to the GPP observations (-11.86 %), followed by GLASS satellite data (-14.85 %). CLM_{grid} had the largest systematic bias with a PBIAS of -24.3 % concerning the ICOS observations.

For ET, the CLM_{grid} again has one of the best approximations to the ICOS observations, only slightly worse than the GLEAM ET (0.64 and 0.63 %). Here again, as with ET, the largest RMSE values correspond to CLM_{pFT} (0.78 %), which, in turn, has the lowest systematic bias (PBIAS of -8.94 %) of the data sources to the ICOS data. Additionally, CLM5 generally underestimates ICOS ET on both levels, while ERA5L, GLASS, and GLEAM all overestimate the ICOS ET. Although opposite signs, the magnitude of the systematic bias in CLM_{grid} is close to that of GLASS and GLEAM. The ERA5L, however, has a relatively large overestimated ET of 31 % on average.

We conclude from this evaluation the following results:

1. CLM_{grid} approximates the observations better than CLM_{pFT} (lower RMSE for both GPP and ET).
2. Nevertheless, CLM_{pFT} shows a lower systematic bias to GPP and ET ICOS observations than CLM_{grid} (lower mean PBIAS).

-
3. Comparing to ERA5L and GLEAM, CLM_{grid} shows a good approximation to the observations, and CLM_{pFT} has the lowest systematic bias of both ET and GPP, attributable to an added value of disaggregation of functional groups in the subgrid.

Note that we focussed on comparing the whole station network at the European continental scale and did not investigate the evaluation metrics of single stations. In summary, the evaluation shows acceptable approximations of CLM5 to the observations and encourages more detailed investigations of ecosystem variability beyond the locations of the ICOS stations.

Yearly cycles of ecosystem processes

Having contextualized the GPP and ET approximations and systematic bias of CLM5 regarding ICOS observations, we continued with more elaborate comparisons against the ICOS site network by grouping sites by vegetation functional types.

We aggregate the time series of each site per group across years to a mean yearly evolution (standard year). Then, the standard years are averaged across space into one time series corresponding to the respective land cover. Please refer to [Figure 7](#).

Figure 7: Mean yearly cycle of GPP aggregated for each land cover (panel) averaged across station locations for each data source (color). Here, CLM5 equals $CLM5_{grid}$.

Note that [Figure 7](#) displays the mean across stations. Here, we confirm the underestimation of observed GPP by all other data sources we identified in the Evaluation that are valid for all land cover. However, we discovered that this underestimation happens predominantly in summer and, to the greatest extent, at DBF sites.

Generally, CLM_{pFT} captures the observed spring transition at ENF sites very well, which is not the case for CLM_{grid} and GLASS data (Figure 7a). On the other hand, the mean ENF summer peak and the autumn transition are estimated better by GLASS. Similarly, CLM_{pFT} exhibits the observed sharp GPP increase in spring nicely (Figure 7b), but all data sources fail to capture the exceptionally high peak in summer there. Similarly, when considering the averages across GRA and CRO sites, it is evident that CLM_{pFT} more accurately captures the observed dynamics throughout the year compared to CLM_{grid} . However, it is worth noting that CLM and the GLASS remote sensing do not provide adequate approximations for the ICOS GRA GPP summer peak duration and the CRO GPP summer peak timing.

Figure 8: Yearly cycle of standard deviation of GPP across stations corresponding to one land cover (panel) across station locations for each data source (color). Here, CLM5 equals $CLM5_{grid}$.

Considering the variation across stations that create this mean yearly evolution, we additionally determine the standard deviation in Figure 8. For instance, a standard deviation of approximately 2 g C m⁻² from ICOS in summer at ENF corresponds to about 25% of the summer peak (8 g C m⁻²). Therefore, there are partly substantial differences between the sites of the same land cover, which may be due to local meteorological conditions during the observations and general differences in climate. The GPP variability within one land cover type is most noticeable in the ICOS observations in GRA during spring and in CRO during summer, which is only slightly apparent in the other data.

Recent studies (Lin et al. 2015; Van Bodegom, Douma, and Verheijen 2014; Caldararu, Purves, and Smith 2015) have also found that observed PFT sites still contain significant variability, indicating shortcomings in the current disaggregation of vegetation function.

[Figure 9](#) depicts the mean yearly evolution of ET across groups of sites with the same land cover type. Again, we can confirm the general slight underestimation of ICOS ET by both CLM5 levels we found previously in the Evaluation and the overestimations by the other data across all selected land cover types. GLEAM is the only data source with a differing systematic bias between land cover types, showing an overestimation in ENF and CRO and an underestimation in DBF and GRA. The disparities between CLM_{grid} and CLM_{PFT} are less noticeable for ET than for GPP. However, there is a substantial overestimation only by CLM_{PFT} at CRO in summer compared to the in-situ observations. On the other hand, CLM_{PFT} represents the spring transition period across all land cover and the DBF summer peak more accurately. CLM5 provides the most consistent and precise approximations to the ET ICOS observations, while ERA5L and GLASS substantially overestimate the ICOS ET summer peak across all land cover types throughout the year.

Figure 9: Mean yearly cycle of ET aggregated for each land cover (panel) averaged across station locations for each data source (color). Here, CLM5 equals CLM_{grid} .

Figure 10: Yearly cycle of standard deviation of ET across stations corresponding to one land cover (panel) across station locations for each data source (color).

The ET ICOS site data variability, expressed as the yearly cycle of the standard deviation across sites (see [Figure 10](#)), is highest across ENF sites and lowest across DBF sites. GLASS data accurately captures the observed variability across ICOS sites at ENF, while both CLM5 levels underestimate it in summer and autumn. Notably, all data sources agree on the low ET variability at DBF sites. Although CLM_{pFT} generally overestimates the ET variability across GRA and CRO sites, it can capture critical dynamics such as the GRA ET variability in the summer trough (see [Figure 10 c](#)) and the peak CRO ET variability in autumn (see [Figure 10 d](#)).

Thus, we conclude from this analysis the following points:

1. CLM5 can capture the land cover type-specific yearly cycles of GPP and ET. CLM_{pFT} captures the specific land cover variability well and approximates the observed mean yearly cycles more accurately than CLM_{grid}. However, there are still shortcomings that need to be addressed.
2. All data sources underestimate ICOS summer GPP, especially at DBF sites.
3. There is a discrepancy between the time series at individual sites, which is smoothed when comparing land cover aggregations. This discrepancy leads to the relatively large RMSE observed in the evaluation.

We now analyze the water-use efficiency, a more complex indicator of ecosystem function that combines GPP and ET.

Water-use efficiency trends

The ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE) is the amount of carbon assimilated per unit of water used. Here, we determine the assimilated carbon as GPP and the water used by the ecosystem as evapotranspiration:

$$WUE = \frac{GPP}{ET}$$

Recent studies (Migliavacca et al. 2021; J. Liang et al. 2023; Peters et al. 2018; Keenan et al. 2013) showed that water-use efficiency is a crucial axis of variability of ecosystem function. The vegetation follows different strategies that control carbon and water fluxes to optimize growth, conserve water resources, or balance both. Therefore, the change in WUE during droughts also indicates the water-use strategy of an ecosystem. Furthermore, the increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentrations cause a partial closure of the plant stomata. This mechanism decreases the water use more than it decreases the carbon uptake, hence increasing WUE.

Furthermore, WUE is an index of ecosystem performance and fitness, giving insights into whether environmental changes or coping well threaten an ecosystem. In summary, WUE is an essential indicator of ecosystem functioning and should be monitored across scales, from leaf, plant, and ecosystem scales to the continental and global scales. In Europe, the increasing drought frequency and severity, increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentrations, and global warming-induced increasing atmospheric dryness affect WUE gradually.

Here, we compare the WUE trends from 1995 to 2018 from the network of EC stations, from remote sensing data, and from CLM_{grid} to identify regions where this axis of ecosystem function changed and potentially indicates an inhibited ecosystem performance due to a changing environment.

First, we only select the summer months of June, July, and August for the analysis. Subsequently, we conduct the seasonal Mann-Kendall analysis pixel-wise. The resulting trend is a Theil-Sen estimator slope, and the p-value of a two-tailed test gives its significance. In Figure 11, we map each pixel's WUE trend, highlighting the regions with significant trends with hatching.

We uncover significantly decreasing WUE trends in central Europe, evident in in-situ, remote sensing, and CLM5 data. The limited geographic representation of the ICOS station network does not yield a clear picture of trends in southern, northern, and eastern Europe. However, eastern Europe shows strong, significant decreasing trends in the remote sensing and CLM5 data. The GLASS remote sensing data also shows significant decreasing trends in central Europe, which CLM5 did not simulate. Both remote sensing and CLM5 again agree on the increasing trends in northern Europe.

Figure 11: Trends of water use efficiency (colormap) from the ICOS stations (left), remote sensing (GLASS), and CLM5_{grid} (right). Stations and regions with a significant trend ($p < 0.05$) are cross-hatched.

Therefore, the conclusions of the European continental WUE trend analysis are as follows:

1. All data sources agree on a decreasing WUE in central Europe.
2. CLM5 and remote sensing show a region of significant WUE decreases in eastern Europe, which could not be captured in the ICOS RI, which underrepresents this region.
3. CLM5 can identify focus regions where ecosystem function shows significant changes, complement the observations, and recommend locations for new stations.

In summary, in the first applications of the European CLM5, we already established an interface between the model and in-situ observations. We identified strengths and shortcomings of the model when comparing it to single sites and aggregated land cover types on grid and PFT levels. Furthermore, CLM5 complemented the observation RI to inform about essential ecosystem functions in areas where stations are unavailable. In the next section, we outline additional research questions that interest the RI with the European CLM5 and the following steps to improve the model setup.

Outlook

Importantly, we will continue our research with the European CLM5 model. On the one hand, the extensive data from the first production run offers plenty of opportunity to conduct further research on changing ecosystem processes on the continental scale. On the other hand, the shortcomings identified in the evaluation demand improvements in the model setup.

Drought response

The continental and long-term data from our European CLM5 enable a comprehensive analysis of ecosystem processes' responses to the continent's increasing drought frequency and severity.

For instance, a recent study (Poppe Terán et al. 2023) of remote sensing data discovered negative precipitation and soil moisture drought responses of WUE throughout Europe. The hydro-climate determines the magnitude and the drivers of the WUE drought response: GPP drives stronger responses in mesic regions, while ET causes weaker responses in arid and humid regions.

However, coarse temporal resolution limits remote sensing data and cannot provide disaggregated data for specific PFTs. Furthermore, the remotely sensed signals miss essential biochemical and ecological feedback processes, which must be included from separate sources to derive ecosystem variables, thereby introducing additional uncertainty. Ultimately, the information derived from remote sensing needs to be more comprehensive to cover the multivariate nature of compound drought events and drought propagation through the Earth system.

Incidentally, the geographical overrepresentation of central Europe in the eLTER RI also results in an overrepresentation of mesic and very humid ecosystems and an underrepresentation of arid regions (see [Figure 12](#)). Given the significant influence of hydro-climate on the drought response of ecosystems, this misrepresentation potentially inhibits a robust assessment of drought response from eLTER observations only.

The European CLM5 outputs enable a spatiotemporally consistent and high-resolved quantification of ecosystem process variability resulting from compound drought events on the continent. Regions exhibiting concerning trends of drought response are potentially threatened in their performance and should be considered as focus regions for the eLTER RI's physical network development.

We will use the European CLM5 outputs to analyze the response of the continent's ecosystem processes to drought. While taking advantage of the abundance of spatiotemporally consistent output variables to implement a holistic and multivariate drought concept, we can evaluate the functional drought response with station data from the eLTER RI. Furthermore, these data provide the opportunity to compare the emerging spatial patterns of the drought response of ecosystem process drivers between CLM5 and remote sensing data in Europe.

Figure 12: Map showing the location of eLTER Sites offering data for this work. The color of the location marker indicates the hydro-climate of the station. See [Figure 4](#) for the spatially resolved hydro-climates across the whole domain.

Input data alternatives

Several studies (Fisher et al. 2019; Song et al. 2020; Post et al. 2018) have reported the sensitivity of CLM5 outputs to its inputs, i.e., the atmospheric forcings or the static surface information. Numerous alternatives exist for the atmospheric forcings and several fields in the surface information, e.g., the land cover and the soil texture data. Of course, any input data set introduces some uncertainty into the model. Therefore, the right choice of input data will play an important role when designing a new setup to increase the robustness of the model outputs and, consequently, the analysis results.

When using the available data for model evaluation, essential aspects are

- Spatial extent and resolution.
- Novelty and precision of the measurements or raw data.
- Novelty and precision of the processing method.
- Intended use of the data.

Our high-resolution land surface setup requires high-resolution input covering the whole CORDEX domain. The currently used atmospheric forcing data, the COSMO-Reanalysis 6, provides the highest resolution in this domain. However, the data only spans the years 1995 - 2018, which does not allow for analysis of more recent drought years (e.g., in 2022). Moreover, it inhibits a more comprehensive BGC spin-up design involving historical periods closer to a natural equilibrium state, and we will use more temporally extensive forcing data from ERA5. It has a lower spatial resolution (30km) than the COSMO-Reanalysis 6 but spans from 1940 to a few months before the present, enabling a better BGC spin-up design and analyses of recent years. Notably, the scientific community widely considers it the most reliable atmospheric data because of its exhaustive coverage and state-of-the-art implementation of data assimilation.

In the present setup, we used the default surface information. Importantly, those data focus on the global scale, and most have a relatively coarse spatial resolution; thus, some may need to be updated. Newer surface data from recently launched satellite missions offer higher resolutions and updated scientific methods. For example, higher resolved land cover data is available using an updated land cover type classification method. These new land cover type distributions will translate into PFT maps and have an impact when assessing spatial patterns of ecosystem functions. Furthermore, new soil texture information in very high-resolution interpolating between an increasing number of local samples would increase the representation of surface heterogeneity in the model.

All in all, updating the atmospheric forcing, land cover, and soil texture in a new CLM5 setup over Europe will:

1. Ensure the state-of-the-art of our model setup.
2. Increase the robustness of analyses conducted on the model outputs.
3. Make the European CLM5 model outputs and eLTER Site observations more comparable.

Enhanced BGC spin-up

Our analyses uncovered a balance between incoming and outgoing ecosystem carbon across PFT in Europe, showing that any ecosystem type emitted as much carbon as it took up, resulting in NEE of $0 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$ (see [Figure 13](#)). This simulated balance contrasts the EC station observations in the ICOS network that identify most sites across PFT and Europe as carbon sinks (taking up more carbon than they emit). Notably, DBF ecosystems exhibit the most significant carbon sink in the observations and, thus, the most considerable discrepancy to the simulated carbon cycle in the European CLM5. The significant underestimation of DBF GPP by CLM5 seen in [Figure 7](#) might be directly related to this.

Figure 13: Mean NEE of aggregated over groups of stations belonging to a certain landcover (marker type) of the observations (x-axis) against the CLM5 (y-axis).

In this light, reflecting on the BGC module in CLM5 and the spin-up conducted before the production runs is essential. In particular, the structure of the BGC model requires the carbon cycle to be in

equilibrium or balance. However, the atmospheric and surface inputs used in the spin-up do not represent an equilibrium state in the real world: Observations identify vegetated ecosystems in Europe as carbon sinks from 1995 through 2018. The null NEE, or carbon balance, we find in the simulations is caused by using the same period of atmospheric forcing in the production runs as in the spin-up, which retains the carbon cycle equilibrium. This spin-up design was due to the limited available years of forcing data from COSMO-Reanalysis 6.

A new CLM5 setup over Europe, including updated inputs described above, enables a more comprehensive spin-up design given the availability of the ERA5 forcings since 1940 (see schematic in [Figure 14](#)). We aim to improve the spin-up for this new setup by considering a forcing period 1950 - 1960, mirroring a climate closer to actual equilibrium conditions. After reaching the equilibrium state at the end of the spin-up, we will conduct a transition simulation from 1960 to 1990. This run considers changes in climate and environment, such as rising temperatures and atmospheric CO₂ levels, that impacted the land surface. Therefore, the model will represent the trends of ecosystem processes during this period. As a result, we hypothesize that carbon sinks will develop for the production runs, which will use the outcome states of the transition period to simulate the years 1990 to 2023. These considerations will enhance the representation of the impact of critical long-term environmental trends on ecosystem processes in the European CLM5.

Figure 14: Schematic of the spin-up design. On the y-axis is the value of an arbitrary variable experiencing a trend over time (x-axis). The dashed line shows the qualitative evolution of the simulated variable with the new spin-up design. The dotted line is the qualitative evolution of the variable of the old spin-up design.

Towards ecosystem reanalysis

Global change has brought complex, interdisciplinary, and interwoven challenges to the research community. In environmental science, researchers depend on state-of-the-art data and methods to understand the interactions between biodiversity, BGC, hydrology, and socio-ecology. The requirements for data sets that support this endeavor are ever-increasing. Accurate, long-term, and holistic sets of data are in high demand. However, in-situ observations are geographically biased, contain systematic and human errors, contain gaps, and are often only available for a specific research sphere (e.g., hydrology). These drawbacks hamper high-quality, holistic science that aims to understand the ecosystem dynamics on the European continent robustly. Therefore, complementary data from remote sensing and models is crucial to provide data fit for eLTER WALES approach. On the other hand, as seen in this report, the model also underlies systematic errors.

Data assimilation fuses a model and observation data, incorporating the model functions while still statistically considering the ground truth data and the uncertainty of both the model and measurements. The outcome consists of gapless, spatiotemporally consistent variable data. The value of reanalysis is, for instance, demonstrated by ERA5. This atmospheric reanalysis is the gold standard of global atmospheric data and has supported numerous research studies in Earth system science and enabled the discovery of emerging interactions between the land surface and the atmosphere. However, the spatial resolution of 30 km in ERA5 is relatively coarse, and the data assimilation step only considers atmospheric observations. This disadvantage leaves room for reanalyses on a finer grid, incorporating observations from whole ecosystems and focussing on surface states, functioning, and processes, known as ecosystem reanalysis (Batz et al. 2021). The emerging eLTER RI already now offers an excellent opportunity to introduce observations directly into the European CLM5 and create an ecosystem reanalysis that would benefit the community across biodiversity, BGC, hydrology, and socio-ecology.

Recently, we conducted the first data assimilation experiments over multiple forested eLTER Sites in Europe. We coupled CLM5 to the Parallel Data Assimilation Framework (PDAF) with the Ensemble Kalman Filter. At a time step where an observation of a variable is available, the variable will be updated in the model, considering the uncertainty of both the observation and the model with Bayesian statistics. Because this update happens live during the simulation, it will affect other states that interact with the respective variable in the model. Ideally, after the assimilation, the updated variable and a set of interconnected variables in the Earth system will be closer to ground truth observations.

We introduced soil moisture measurements into 1D setups of CLM5 for each site, hypothesizing that this would increase the representation of soil moisture and further evapotranspiration. While the updated soil moisture was closer to the observations (reduced RMSE), the simulated evapotranspiration did not improve. This result points to complex interactions between soil moisture and vegetation through highly uncertain soil hydrology and vegetation parameters and processes. The way forward is enhancing the representation of evapotranspiration and carbon uptake towards a holistic ecosystem reanalysis, including updating soil and vegetation parameters during the data assimilation procedure and possibly assimilating observed vegetation states, such as the leaf area

index. Thus, we are currently developing the CLM5 data assimilation framework for the following cases:

1. Soil and vegetation parameter updates over multiple eLTER Sites.
2. Data assimilation of vegetation states over multiple eLTER Sites.
3. Data assimilation of soil moisture and leaf area index from eLTER Sites over Europe with the continental CLM5 setup.
4. Creation of a European ecosystem reanalysis data set.

Conclusions and recommendations

This deliverable details a pan-European continental scale terrestrial ecosystem model (CLM5) setup and its interfaces with the eLTER RI. We describe the geographical domain for which we are setting up the model, the model structure, input data, and the procedure of the BGC spin-up.

European CLM5 evaluation

Furthermore, we showed the performance of the simulations by comparing in-situ observations from eLTER co-located ICOS sites, yielding promising results of the CLM5 model. Comparing the CLM5 PFT sub-grid layer time series that corresponds with the station land cover type to its observations reduces the systematic error compared to the aggregated cell values. However, the RMSE of CLM5 PFT is generally larger than the grid cell values. Analyzing the representation of the observed yearly evolution of evapotranspiration and gross primary production per plant functional type of the simulations from 1995 - 2018 revealed systematic underestimations of ET and GPP across all land cover types. An improved setup of CLM5, including more recent data and an enhanced spin-up design, may fix the described systemic errors.

More advanced examinations of WUE trends from remote sensing and CLM5 found a firm agreement on declining trends in Central and Eastern Europe, indicating potentially threatened ecosystems. Observation data from the RI cannot fully confirm our findings because of the misrepresentation of the Eastern European region. Therefore, we encourage special consideration of Eastern Europe when advancing the eLTER RI network design.

Overall, we tested and showed potential synergies between a terrestrial ecosystem model over Europe and the eLTER RI and highlighted further critical model and RI development needs. Further efforts in the RI and this European ecosystem model would increase the robust understanding of ecosystems and produce actionable insights for stakeholders.

Synergies of a European CLM5 and eLTER RI across scales

Then, we considered the implications of the scale difference between the model and the station measurements and how these scales might synergize:

- Land surface heterogeneity within the 3 km x 3 km grid cell might hamper the comparability of in-situ data to the closest grid cell in the European model.
- The existing station network is biased and overrepresents Central Europe, humid hydro-climates, and forest ecosystems.
- CLM5 allows the analysis of PFT-specific time series in the sub-grid layer corresponding to the station land cover type.
- Further, the sizeable continental extent of our European CLM5 model has the potential to identify areas of interest for new eLTER Sites. For instance, areas where CLM5 ecosystem processes show significant trends, but no measurements are yet available.
- The model can project patterns found in the in-situ observations in space (to the whole European domain) and in time (e.g., future projections).
- On the other hand, in-situ data is the only source to assess the CLM5 outputs robustly.

- The European CLM5 and in-situ station data can be combined to create a valuable ecosystem reanalysis data set through the assimilation of the observations directly into the observations.
- Importantly, recent studies show that functional land cover types and PFT disaggregation do not explain significant variability in ecosystem processes. Thus, new methods to group vegetation into functional groups, integrating biodiversity, hydrology, BGC, and socio-ecology, are currently being developed. The eLTER RI and the WAILS approach can play an essential role in advancing this research. For instance, a novel CLM5 calibration method could use eLTER data to calibrate CLM5 parameters to local ecosystem traits. Thus, Earth system science and model development could greatly benefit from the holistic eLTER data perspective.

Recommendations for IT services

In this work, we depended on homogenized in-situ measurements of multiple stations across the whole RI physical network. Crucially, developing our large-scale analysis is straightforward as long as the data format is consistent across the sites. While most of the requested data was delivered, station PIs did not coherently stick to the suggested data format for that call. General site metadata was accessible through the eLTER Site-Registry (DEIMS SDR portal), but a more comprehensive set of site metadata (e.g., more information on species composition and annual sums, means or even time-series of meteorological variables) is crucial to bring together researchers across disciplines for WAILS.

In its current emerging form, eLTER already provides essential access to information and links to other RIs that facilitate continental scale ecosystem research. However, there is still room for improvement that should be considered toward an established RI. To further support impactful, large-scale, and whole systems research in the eLTER RI, we recommend the development of:

- A central metadata portal with exhaustive general information about the site.
- A central data download center for time series data from the whole RI.
- Data sets that bundle sites and variables using a standard data format.
- A web portal offering possible supplementary data from satellites and models and their comparison to the eLTER observations.

RI co-location

Due to the lack of easily accessible and homogenized data currently in eLTER, and station PIs pointing to the ICOS data portal during the data calls, we leveraged the co-location with the ICOS RI.

Importantly, data on the carbon cycle is essential for eLTER, providing abiotic data for the BGC and hydrology spheres. Sites that are part of the ICOS RI and the eLTER RI fulfill the protocols for both RIs and are thus well-equipped to support transdisciplinary research. For example, a combination of eLTER biodiversity data and the ICOS flux data enables research on the biodiversity control of ecosystem processes. Further, socio-ecological factors collected in eLTER, such as the prevailing industry in the region, can be considered when assessing drivers of the carbon uptake in European ecosystems. These results are essential for understanding contemporary ecosystem dynamics and implementing that holistic understanding into Earth system models.

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